

Preliminary research on the application of neural networks to the combustion control of boilers with automatic firing

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Abstract— This paper deals with the importance and application of neural networks for improving the operation of boilers with automatic firing. Although the neural network model was illustrated in the middle of the twentieth century, it is experiencing its full expansion only today. Neural networks have a very wide application, both in complex security systems, improving the quality of life through applications used in everyday life, and in industrial plants. The paper starts from the theoretical foundations for understanding neural networks and provides an overview of research conducted on boilers with automatic firing. The conclusion of the work is that this area is insufficiently researched and that a greater application of neural networks in this area would be of great importance for improving combustion, and thus would lead to significant fuel savings and reduction of environmental pollution..

Keywords – neural networks, boilers with automatic firing, environmental protection

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, when we are faced with uncontrolled pollution, and at the same time, the sale of boilers with automatic firing is expanding, we must take care of saving the fuel that the boiler consumes. By increasing the degree of fuel utilization, we reduce the emission of harmful gases into the atmosphere, reduce the consumption of biomass

or fossil fuels that are used, and therefore have a positive effect on the environment and increase the quality of living conditions. Neural networks, although they were presented as a mathematical model in the middle of the twentieth century, are experiencing their full expansion only today, at the end of the first quarter of the twenty-first century. The application of neural networks is very broad, there is almost no area in which they have not played a key role in the functioning of automatic control systems, object recognition, decision systems and many other areas that we are surrounded by.[1] The application of neural networks in the combustion control of boilers with automatic firing is almost negligible. There is almost no research on this topic in works and practical application. The application of neural networks itself could be reflected in the automatic calibration of the combustion control system.

II. NEURON NETWORKS - THEORETICAL BASICS

Interest in neural networks dates back to early 1940s, as illustrated by the work of McCulloch and Pitts [2]. As a basis for modeling neural systems, they proposed models of neurons in the form of binary boundary devices and stochastic

algorithms that include instant changes from 0 to 1 or from 1 to 0 in the output of the neurons.

The results of Rumelhart, Hinton, and Williams [3], dealing with the development of training algorithms for multilayer perceptrons, changed significantly the state of development of neural networks. Their basic method, often called the generalized delta rule for backward propagation learning, provides an effective training method for multilayer networks. Although it cannot be shown that this training algorithm converges to a solution in terms of analogous proof for a single-layer perceptron, the generalized delta rule has been successfully used in a number of problems of practical interest. This success established perceptron-like multilayer machines as one of the major neural network models currently in use.

Perceptron for two classes of patterns in its most basic form, the perceptron learns a linear decision function that discriminates two linearly separable training sets. The response of this elementary decision mechanism is calculated as a weighted sum of its inputs; it is

$$d(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i x_i + \omega_{n+1} \quad (1)$$

This decision function is linear with respect to the components of the pattern vector. The coefficients ω_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n, n + 1$, called synaptic weights, scale the inputs before they are summed together and passed through a threshold function. In this sense, weights are analogous to synapses in the human neural system. The threshold function that maps the output of the summator to the final output of the device is often called the activation function.

When $d(x) > 0$, the threshold element causes the perceptron output to be +1, indicating that the pattern k is recognized as belonging to class i . The inverse is true when $d(x) < 0$. When $d(x) = 0$, the input vector lies on the decision surface that separates the two classes of patterns, giving an absence of decision. The decision limit implemented by a perceptron is obtained by equating the previous equation with zero:

$$d(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i x_i + \omega_{n+1} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Another form that is often used is to extend the pattern vector by adding an additional unitary value to that vector. That is, an extended

sample vector is created from the sample vector x . The previous equation then becomes

$$d(y) = \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i y_i = w^t y \quad (3)$$

This expression is usually more appropriate in terms of notation. However, regardless of the formulation used, the key problem is to find w using a given set of training template vectors from each of the two classes.

In multilayer neural networks, we apply the decision-making functions to recognition problems of multiclass patterns, regardless of whether classes are separable or not. These networks consist multiple layers of perceptron computing elements.

The basic architecture of the neural network model under consideration consists of layers of structurally identical computer nodes (neurons) arranged so that the output of each neuron in one layer is fed to the input of each neuron in the next layer. The number of neurons in the first layer, layer A, is N_A . Often, $N_A = n$, i.e. the size of the input sample vector. The number of neurons in the output layer, layer Q, is denoted by N_Q . The number N_Q is equal to W , the number of pattern classes that the neural network is trained to recognize. The network recognizes the sample vector x as belonging to class ω_i if the network output for that class is "high", while outputs for all other classes are "low", as explained in the following paragraphs.

Each neuron has the same structure as that in the perceptron model we discussed earlier, with the exception that the hard limiter activation function has been replaced by a soft-limiting "sigmoid" function. Differentiability along all neural network pathways is required in the development of training rules. The following sigmoid activation function has the necessary differentiability property:

$$h_j(l_j) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(l_j + \theta_j)/\theta_v}} \quad (4)$$

When this special function is used, the system gives a high reading for any value of l_j greater than θ_j , and a low reading for any value of l_j , less than θ_j . The sigmoid activation function is always positive and can reach its limit values of 0 and 1 only if the input for the activation element is infinitely negative or positive, respectively. For this reason, values

close to 0 and 1 (say, 0.05 and 0.95) define low and high values at neuron output. In principle, different types of activation functions can be used for different layers or even for different nodes in the same layer of the neural network. In practice, the usual approach is to use the same form of activation function throughout the network.

During training, adjusting the neurons' parameters in the output layer is simple, because the desired output of each node is known. The main problem in training a multilayer network lies in adjusting the weights in the so-called hidden layers. That is, in those that are not the output layer.

Back-propagation training method: We start from the output layer. The total squared error, i.e. the difference between the desired responses, r_q and the corresponding actual responses, O_q , of the nodes in the (output) layer Q, is

$$E_Q = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{q=1}^{N_q} (r_q - O_q)^2 \quad (5)$$

where N_q is the number of nodes in the output layer.

All these equations form a generalized delta rule for training a multilayer neural network. The process begins with an arbitrary (but not all equal) set of weights across the network. Then the application of the generalized delta rule in any iterative step involves two basic phases. In the first phase, the training vector is presented to the grid and allowed to propagate through the layers to calculate the output O, for each node. The outputs of a node in the output layer are then compared to their desired responses, r_p , to generate the error terms. The second phase involves propagating backwards through the network, during which the corresponding error signal is passed to each node and appropriate weight changes are made. This procedure also applies to bias weights of the perceptrons. As previously explained in some detail, they are treated simply as additional weights that modify the sum of inputs of a node in the network.

It is a common practice to monitor the overall classification errors as well as the errors associated with individual patterns. In a successful training session, the classification errors decrease with the number of iterations and the procedure converges to a stable set of

weights, that show only small fluctuations with additional training. The approach used to determine whether a pattern is properly classified during training is to determine whether the node response in the output layer associated with the pattern class from which the pattern was derived is high, while all other nodes have low outputs, such as as previously defined.

Once the system is trained, it classifies the patterns using the parameters established during the training phase. In normal operation, all feedback paths are excluded. Each input sample is then allowed to propagate through all the layers, and the pattern is classified as belonging to the output node class that was high, while all others were low. If more than one output is marked as high, or if none of the outputs is marked as such, the choice is one of declaring a misclassification or simply assigning a pattern to the class of the output node with the highest numerical value. [1]

III. APPLICATION OF NEURON NETWORKS IN BOILERS WITH AUTOMATIC FIRING

The boiler is one of the three major devices of the thermal power plant. The single-unit capacity of the boilers in power plants is constantly rising, and the boilers are developing toward large capacity and high parameters. [4, 5] For large or very large coal-fired boilers (supercritical units), if the combustion instability occurs during combustion, the thermal efficiency of boiler combustion will directly decrease, and a large number of pollution by-products will be generated, even some extreme situations may occur, such as furnace cavity extinction and major furnace safety accidents. [6,7]

One of the applications of neural networks in boilers with automatic firing is given in the work of Zhang in 2020, where thermal energy diagnostics of boilers is done using computer recognition of objects and neural networks. The computer image processing and neural network technology are applied to diagnose the thermal energy of boiler plants, i. e., the flame combustion diagnosis, to verify their effectiveness and superiority. Methods: First, the YD-NQ type endoscopic high temperature video acquisition system is used to collect the images of flame combustion. Second, the images are pre-processed by the gray-scale method and the median filtering method. Then the flame

combustion parameter features are extracted. The neural network algorithm is improved, and the boiler combustion model based on the improved neural network algorithm is established. Therefore, the combustion decision base is obtained. Finally, the improved neural network model is compared with the traditional neural network model and the 5-4 model to verify its validity. Results: The experiments have found that the improved neural network model is superior to the traditional neural network model. Meanwhile, its accuracy rate and confidence are relatively higher than those of the traditional model. In addition, a single sample also consumes shorter running time, which is 0.0075 seconds. Comparing with the 5-4 model, the improved neural network model has certain advantages, i. e., its accuracy rate and confidence are relatively higher, which are, respectively 91.28% and 96.69%, however, a single sample consumes longer running time than the 5-4 model. Conclusion: The experimental research has found that the application of computer image processing and neural network technology to the thermal energy diagnosis of boiler plants can effectively determine the stability of flame combustion, timely understand the state of flame combustion, and thus diagnose the thermal energy. Therefore, they have values for applications. [8]

Another example of the application of neural networks in boilers with automatic firing is given in the work of Chen Ji in 2022. There is described a random spectral attenuation method proposed to reduce moisture content disturbances. The calibration spectra were replicated and multiplied by random attenuation coefficients to introduce information about the possible interference. All of the simulated attenuated spectra were used to train the artificial neural network (ANN) quantitative model. Compared with direct modeling without random spectral attenuation, the coefficient of determination (R2) was improved from -3.4291 to 0.7102 , and the root-mean-square error (RMSE) was reduced from 1.8709% to 0.4786% in the analysis of volatile matter content interfered by moisture. The results showed sufficient ability of the method to detect samples disturbed by moisture without additional sample pretreatment and improve the speed of LIBS analysis. [9]

One of the most significant and extensive works describing the application of neural networks in boiler control is Hang Ta Wen's work from 2021. The purpose of his study is to

utilize two artificial intelligence (AI) models to predict the syngas composition of a fixed bed updraft gasifier for the gasification of rice husks. Air and steam-air mixtures are the gasifying agents. In the present work, the feeding rate of rice husks is kept constant, while the air and steam flow rates vary in each case. The consideration of various operating conditions provides a clear comparison between air and steam-air gasification. The effects of the reactor temperature, steam-air flow rate, and the ratio of steam to biomass are investigated here. The concentrations of combustible gases such as hydrogen, carbon monoxide, and methane in syngas are increased when using the steam-air mixture. Two AI models, namely artificial neural network (ANN) and gradient boosting regression (GBR), are applied to predict the syngas compositions using the experimental data. A total of 74 sets of data are analyzed. The compositions of five gases (CO, CO₂, H₂, CH₄, and N₂) are predicted by the ANN and GBR models. The coefficients of determination (R²) range from 0.80 to 0.89 for the ANN model, while the value of R² ranges from 0.81 to 0.93 for GBR model. In this study, the GBR model outperforms the ANNs model based on its ensemble technique that uses multiple weak learners. As a result, the GBR model is more convincing in the prediction of syngas composition than the ANN model considered in this research. [10]

IV. CONCLUSION

The safe and stable operation of the boilers often determines the safe and environmentally friendly operation of the entire unit. The most direct indication of the stability of combustion is the combustion flame. Therefore, it is necessary to monitor the combustion state of the flame in the furnace chamber in real-time to ensure the safe and economic operation of the boilers. The way to establish a safe and reliable energy-saving furnace coal combustion system has become a critical issue. [11, 12] Until now, the monitoring system has only remained the stage of monitoring whether the coal particles are in the state of being lit or extinguished. Although a boiler flame image monitoring system can be introduced to provide technical support for automatic monitoring and determination of combustion stability, flame stability monitoring requires relevant personnel to perform on-site observations. Therefore, the stabilization of flame images has always been one of the urgent

problems to be solved in the automatic monitoring of the state of combustion of boilers. A scientific and effective solution to this problem is important for ensuring the safe and economical operation of boilers. [8] Although there are systems with better results (GBR model), the use of knowledge from the field of neural networks for application in combustion control in boilers with automatic ignition would greatly improve the degree of fuel utilization, ensure more stable operation of boilers, which would lead to significant energy savings, and therefore would help preserve the environment, reduce the emission of harmful gases, reduce the amount of ash and reduce the consumption of biomass and fossil fuels, which are becoming less and less every day on planet Earth.

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